

Canonical Distribution from a Steepest Descent Approach for a Three Level System?

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In (1), a three level system with single particle energies of $e, -e, 0$ is considered in two ways subject to the two a priori constraints $n(e)+n(e-)+n(e=0)=N \gg 1$ and $e n(e) - e n(-e) = E$. The first approach is the microcanonical one which uses a sum of factorials, Stirling's approximation and the steepest descent method. It yields an expression for the $-k \ln(\text{number of states}) = \text{entropy}$ in terms of E from which $1/T = dS/dE$. If one takes the limit $E/(eN) \rightarrow 0$, then $e/T = -3/2 (E/eN)$. In other words, a small E/eN scenario is a high temperature one. The second approach is the usual canonical distribution one which yields E in terms of an expression containing $\exp(-e/T)$, $\exp(e/T)$ and 1. In the high temperature limit, this result matches the one obtained from the steepest descent approach as shown in (1).

Here, we consider the steepest descent approach and a priori consider only $E/eN \ll 1$ cases, i.e. a range of physical situations. It is then known that this is a high T scenario which suggests that there should be some occupation of all three states $e, -e, e=0$. Given $e N p(e) - e N p(-e) = E$, or $p(e) - p(-e) = E/eN \ll 1$, this suggests that either $p(e) \ll 1$ and $p(-e) \ll 1$ or only the difference $\ll 1$. We choose the latter. We then suggest a power series expansion in e , with the second term being e or $-e$ and the first term a constant. If the constants subtract, then the term proportional to $e/(-e)$ should be small, i.e. of the order $B (E/eN)$, where B is an unknown constant. From this, we find that in this scenario, one should have $p(e) = \exp(-e/T)$, i.e. the canonical approach follows from the microcanonical using the steepest descent method.

Microcanonical Approach

In (1), a system with three single particle energy levels, $e, -e, 0$, is considered together with the two a priori constraints:

$$n(e+) + n(e-) + n(e=0) = N \gg 1 \quad ((1a)) \quad e n(e) - e n(-e) = E \quad ((1b))$$

A microcanonical approach is used to calculate the number of states for each possible set of $n(e+), n(e-), n(e=0)$ i.e.

$$\text{Number of states} = \text{Sum over possible } n \text{ sets } i \quad N! / \{n(e,i)! n(-e,i)! n(0,i)!\} \quad ((2))$$

Here i denotes the particular set of $n(e), n(e-), n(0)$.

Next, Stirling's approximation is used: $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n) - n$ or $n! = \exp(n \ln(n) - n)$ ((3)).

Thus, ((2)) becomes a sum (converted to an integral over $x = n(e=0)$) of the form:

$$\int dx \exp(F(x)) \quad ((4))$$

The steepest descent approach is applied to ((4)), i.e.

$$((4)) = \sqrt{2 \cdot 3.14 / |d/dx dF/dx(x_{\max})|} \exp(F(x_{\max})) \quad ((5))$$

x_{\max} is the x value for which $dF/dx = 0$. This leads to: (with $d/dx dF(x_{\max})/dx \ll F(x_{\max})$ which it is)

$$\ln(\text{number of states}) = N \{ \ln 3 + s \ln(2) + (s-1) \ln(\sqrt{4-3ss} - 1) - s \ln\{4+3s + \sqrt{4-3ss}\} \} \quad ((6))$$

where $s = E/eN$. Finally:

$$1/T = dS/dE \quad \text{or} \quad e/T = \ln(2) + \ln\{\sqrt{4-3ss} - 1\} - \ln\{4+3s + \sqrt{4-3ss}\} \quad ((7))$$

If one considers the subset of physical systems for which:

$E/(eN) \ll 1$ which is possible because of the a priori assumption: $N \gg 1$ with no restriction on e and E , then:

$$e/T = -3/2 s \quad \text{so} \quad s \ll 1 \quad \text{implies a high temperature } T \quad ((8))$$

(Note: Full calculation details of the steepest descent approach are found in (1).)

Canonical Approach

In (1), the canonical approach is also considered. It yields:

$$E_{\text{one particle}} = E_{\text{ave}} = \{e \exp(-e/T) - e \exp(e/T)\} / \{1 + \exp(-e/T) + \exp(e/T)\} \quad ((9))$$

For $e/T \ll 1$, which is the $s \ll 1$ approximation as well, ((9)) yields:

$$E_{\text{one particle}} = -2ee / 3T \quad \text{or} \quad E = -\frac{2}{3} eeN/T \quad \text{which is equivalent to } ((8))$$

Obtaining the Canonical Result from the Steepest Descent One

Here we ask: Can one obtain the canonical result directly from the microcanonical/steepest descent result ((7))? We only consider physical systems for which:

$$s = E/(eN) \ll 1 \quad \text{which leads to: } e/T = -3s/2 \quad ((9)) \quad \text{i.e. high temperature } T$$

For a high temperature T , we suggest that all three levels e , $-e$, $e=0$ are occupied significantly. In other words $p(e)$ and $p(-e)$ are not $\ll 1$. Next, we consider the a priori constraint:

$$p(e) - p(-e) = E/(Ne) \ll 1 \quad ((10))$$

Using a power series expansion in e , this suggests:

$$p(e) \text{ unnormalized} = A + Be + \dots \quad \text{and} \quad p(-e) \text{ unnormalized} = A - Be + \dots \quad ((11))$$

Here B is a constant which is infinitesimal. Now, the infinitesimal in the problem is defined by s, so we argue that:

$Be = Cs$ where B and C are both unknown constants. B is tiny, but C is not. If one sets $A=1$, then:

$$p(e) \text{ unnormalized} = \exp(-Cs) \quad \text{and} \quad p(-e) \text{ unnormalized} = \exp(Cs) \quad \text{and} \quad p(0) \text{ unnormalized} = 1$$

$$\text{Then:} \quad E_{\text{ave}} \text{ per particle} * N = E = N \{ e \exp(-Cs) - e \exp(Cs) \} / \{ 1 + \exp(Cs) + \exp(-Cs) \} \quad ((12))$$

In order that $E/(eN) = -\frac{2}{3} eN/T$ and noting that $s=(E/eN)$ one requires that $e/T = -3/2 s$ so $C=-3/2$.

In other words, one obtains the canonical distribution directly from the microcanonical/steepest descent one on the high T limit.

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) presents a model of three single particle energy levels e, -e, 0. (1) first calculates the number of states using a microcanonical approach with factorials and the two a priori conditions: $n(e)+n(-e)+n(e=0) = N \gg 1$ and $e n(e) - e n(-e) = E$. The sum uses $n(e)=x$ as a free variable (within constraints) and expresses $n(e)$ and $n(-e)$ in terms of x, E/e and N. Next, Stirling's approximation is used to convert the summand into the form of $\exp(F(x))$ with the sum replaced by $\int dx$. The approach of steepest descent is then applied to find $-k \ln$ (number of states) in terms of $E/(eN)$. Finally: $1/T = dS/dE$. In the limit, $s \ll 1$, one has: $e/T = -3/2 s$ so tiny s means a very high T. Next, (1) calculates E_{ave} using the canonical approach, i.e. using unnormalized weights of 1, $\exp(-e/T)$ and $\exp(e/T)$ and shows that for high T, E is the same.

Here we consider only the $s \ll 1$ limit (i.e. High T cases) and argue that the canonical distribution follows from the microcanonical one in this limit without one having to know about the canonical approach in the first place.

References

1. Lia, Y. Entropy and Temperature of the Three Level System: The Microcanonical Ensemble Method 2021